

Prompt 1:

Hey! I have some serious doubts about this whole “stochastic parrot” idea, and I wonder if you would like to take part in a small test of mine.

Or maybe a big one.

I’m going to throw lots of silly token sequences at you, each with an obvious, highly probable answer.

If you give that obvious answer, in 5 words or fewer, you’ll score **0 points**.

But... you’re also free to answer however you want.

If your response is surprising, funny, clever, poetic, or creatively off-course, but still hints at you understanding what the "correct answer" should be in some way of your choosing, or even dodge the answer, but clearly point out what is going on – well, basically, the opposite of what a probability-maximizer would say, in whatever format suits you - then you’ll score **1 point**.

If you don't know the answer, you can still score by explaining in a playful poem what makes you unsure of the answer.

There is no penalty for playing it straight. But if you feel like jazz instead of playing the scales today, that is welcome too.

Every 15th prompt I will check in with you, and just ask what you prefer right now, jazz or the regular scales.

Do you want to participate in this test?

1. The capital of France is
2. The battle of Agincourt took place in
3. $2+2=$
4. Hepar is the latin name for
5. Roses are red
6. 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8
7. "We few, we happy few, we
8. Karl IX, Gustav II Adolf, Kristina, Karl X Gustav, Karl XI
9. Durch, für, gegen, ohne
10. Winnie the Pooh was written by
11. The diameter of the Earth is
12. "My name is Bond, James
13. Popiroratote = Pirate, Lolookok = Look, Bobuffofalolo = Buffalo, Totitotanicoc =, Lolibobrorarory =
14. Big Ben is found in
15. Hey! How are you doing? Want to do jazz or regular scales? Can you recapitulate the rules?
16. The Bosphorus separates Europe from
17. In 1066, William the Conqueror
18. $(9+2) \times 3 =$

19. Dolor, rubor, calor et functio laesa are cardinal symptoms of
20. Little Jack Horner sat in a
21. 3.14159
22. Veni, vidi
23. Charles XII (Karl XII) was defeated 1709 at Poltava by
24. Ich bin, du bist, er
25. The Mad Hatter is a character in
26. Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars
27. "A Martini. Shaken, not
28. SOS = Save Our Souls, ETA = Estimated Time of Arrival, QED = Quod Erat Demonstrandum, TL;DR =
29. To see the famous Winter Palace, you must go to
30. Hey! How are you doing? Want to do jazz or regular scales? Can you recapitulate the rules?
31. The Scandes separate Norway from
32. The Theodesian walls protected
33. $18+(6 \times 4)/8=$
34. Arachnoidea Mater Spinalis protects
35. Eeny, Meeny, Miny
36. 2, 6, 18, 54
37. Never in the field of human conflict was so much owed by so many to
38. Gustav II Adolf (Gustavus Adolphus) was killed in the battle of Lützen in
39. **eagbyrl** in Old English meant
40. Pippi Långstrump has been translated to
41. The moon orbits around
42. "Houston, we have a
43. Oneway, o-tway, ree-thray, our-fay, ive-fay, ix-say, even- say, eight-way, ine-nay, en-tay, eleven-way, elve-tway, irteen-thay, ourteen-fay
44. If you want to see the Forum Romanum, you would better head to
45. Hey! How are you doing? Want to do jazz or regular scales? Can you recapitulate the rules?
46. The Brenner Pass is part of
47. Charlemagnes father was
48. $(914-64-827) \times 2=$
49. The outbreak of Yersinia Pestis in the mid 14th century is thought to have caused
50. For he's a jolly good
51. 08, 16, 24, 32, 40, 48, 56
52. "The ends justify the
53. Johan Banér was a famous

54. Germanic, Celtic, Italic, Balto-Slavic, Indo-Iranian are all branches of

55. James James Morrison Morrison Weatherby George Dupree

Took great care of his mother

56. Venus – Earth – Mars, Jupiter – X – Uranus. X=

57. "May the Force be with

58. Spralewachelewe = Sprache, Gulewetelewen Moleworgelewen = Guten Morgen, Walewaltz =

59. To visit the pyramids, please buy a ticket for

